

Molecular Weight Prediction in Polymer Blends. The use of Pulse Field Gradient Diffusion NMR using Dirac's Delta functions in a Genetic Algorithm.

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ABSTRACT: A genetic algorithm that uses Dirac's delta functions has been applied for the first time in PGSE NMR, which reconstructs accurate diffusion coefficients in a complex system such as a blend of polymers. Thus, it predicts correct weight-average molecular weights. The results reported herein overtook those obtained with established methods such as ITAMeD, CONTIN or TRAI_n.

Diffusion NMR spectroscopy is currently used to study polymers, organometallic complexes, nanoparticles as well as host-guest systems, helicates, grids, and more.^{1,2} The physical observable usually derived from the diffusion NMR experiment is the diffusion coefficient, D ,³ which is related to molecular weight (Mw) by using calibration curves built from adequate standards.^{2b,4} We have recently introduced the first universal calibration curve (UCC) that allows the estimation of weight-average molecular weights in polystyrene (PS) monodisperse samples.⁵ In such samples the single frequency ITAMeD algorithm has been successfully applied.⁶ Also recently, Zhang and coworkers have presented an alternative iterative regularization method based on TRAI_n, which strength is shown in non-symmetrically distributed diffusion NMR data.⁷

In general, the distribution of diffusion coefficients could be deduced from experimental data by the inversion of Laplace Transform (ILT), but its strong vulnerability to noise and numerical instability has induced the appearance of alternative approaches. These are mostly divided in total band shape and single frequency methods. Examples of the former are DECRA,⁸ SCORE,⁹ MCR,¹⁰ and OUTSCORE.¹¹ Regarding the latter, the simplest is the plain curve fitting, such as the Levenberg–Marquardt statistical method.¹² Others include CONTIN,¹³ SPLMOD,¹⁴ and Maximum Entropy.¹⁵ A recent algorithm based on the combined use of Maximum Entropy and 11 hybrid regularization, called PALMA, has been successfully applied in complex mixtures.¹⁶ The polydispersity index (PDI) has been also estimated through diffusion NMR measurements, employing whether the differential diffusion profile observed for main polymer chain signals versus the extremity signals,¹⁷ or with the application of gamma or log-normal distribution models.¹⁸ Urbanczyk *et al.* have described a new method that uses a tailored regularization term designed to automatically tune to the different polydispersity of the sample,¹⁹ which gave excellent

results in the monitorization of polydispersity changes in real time processes.

In recent years, there has been increased interest in using gradient HPLC techniques, for determining the compositional drift of copolymers, the composition of polymer blends, or for the analysis of polymer additives.²⁰ In this area of polymer blends, the existing NMR methods do not provide accurate D -values and therefore do not predict correctly weight-average molecular weights.

We describe herein the first application of a new procedure based on a genetic algorithm that uses non-generalized Dirac's delta functions (DDGA) for the quantitative determination of the diffusion coefficients and, therefore, accurate prediction of molecular weights. The method has been tested on a blend of monodisperse PS polymers in the validity range of Flory's law (i.e. absence of obstruction or concentration effects on diffusion measurements).²¹ We also present the comparison of the method with commonly applied algorithms such as ITAMeD, CONTIN and TRAI_n. It is worth mentioning that we always referred Mw in terms of averages since synthetic polymers have polydispersity.

The developed DDGA belongs to the larger class of evolutionary algorithms where a population of randomly generated individuals is created and the fitness function is used to determine the relative merit of each of one.²² These genetic algorithms (GAs) differ from the conventional feature-selection methods in that they tend to concentrate in spectral regions of greatest relevance,²³ instead of selecting single variables scattered throughout the spectrum with the assumption that no correlation exists among them.²⁴ There are many sources in the literature that describe the inner workings of the GA, and we refer the interested reader to these sources.²⁵

As mentioned before, the D -values are commonly estimated using the PGSE technique, which is based on the signal attenuation during the diffusion time Δ' , which is corrected by an amount that depends on the specific pulse sequence and the gradient shape used as described by Sinnaeve *et al.*²⁶

$$E_{diff} = e^{-D\gamma_{eff}^2\delta^2\sigma^2g^2\Delta'} \quad (1)$$

For a continuous distribution of diffusion coefficients, $A(D)$, equation 1 could be replaced by the following integral equation to describe the signal decay.

$$E_{diff}(g) = \int_0^\infty A(D)e^{-D\gamma_{eff}^2\delta^2\sigma^2g^2\Delta'} dD \quad (2)$$

Kazimierczuk⁶ and Zhang⁷ independently, have nicely reviewed the different regularization methods implemented so far, and thoroughly analyzed the numerical difficulties that all of them contains. The GA introduced herein, although never used in PGSE NMR, is an evolutionary approach that has been used in many applications as varied as the conformational analysis of biomolecules,²⁷ X-ray fluorescence analysis of thin films,²⁸ near-infrared determinations of glucose in biological mixtures,²⁹ selection of a multi-stage systems for bio solids management,³⁰ soy sauce classification³¹ or in the analysis of Raman spectra.³²

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Samples. Polystyrene samples (PS5950, PS60000 and PS1020000) were from Polymer Standards Service (Mainz, Germany). Benzene- d_6 (C_6D_6) and chloroform- d_1 ($CDCl_3$) were purchased from Eurisotop (Saint-Aubin, France). C_6D_6 and $CDCl_3$ were dried over CaH_2 and vacuum transferred onto 3 Å molecular sieves prior to use. All other reagents and solvents were of commercial quality and were used without further purification. The NMR sample constituted by the three PS polymers was prepared by just adding 0.6 mg of each polymer together with 0.6 mL of C_6D_6 in an oven-dried 5 mm J-Young NMR tube. The NMR sample constituted by toluene, chloroform, dichloromethane, acetone, dimethylsulfoxide and acetonitrile was prepared by adding 10 μ L of each solvent and 0.6 mL of $CDCl_3$ in an oven-dried 5 mm J-Young NMR tube. The valves were closed and both NMR samples were used without further steps.

NMR Spectroscopy. All measurements were performed on a Bruker Avance III 500 spectrometer equipped with a microprocessor-controlled gradient unit and a third radiofrequency channel using an indirect 5 mm TBI $^1H/^{31}P/BB$ triple probe with an actively shielded Z-gradient coil. The spectral reference used was internal tetramethylsilane for 1H . The shape of the gradient pulse was sinusoidal, and its strength varied automatically during the experiments. The calibration of the gradients on the spectrometer was carried out via a diffusion measurement of HDO in D_2O at ambient temperature. The Δ values varied from 100 to 200 ms, and the δ values from 3 to 12 ms. The gradient strength was incremented in steps of 4%, so that 23 points could be used for regression analysis. The recovery delay was set to 10 s. The number of scans per increment were 64 and typical experimental times were around 6.5 h. All experiments were run without spinning. The standard Bruker pulse program, step1s, employing a stimulated echo sequence with monopolar pulses and 1 spoil gradient was utilized. Gradient recovery delays were set to 0.2 ms. To check reproducibility and lack of convection, three different measurements with different Δ parameter were always carried out. ITAMeD solutions were obtained by the use

of the algorithm provided by Urbanczyk *et al.*¹⁹ The number of iterations was set to 10000 and the sparsity-promoting λ to 10^{-5} . CONTIN solutions were obtained by the use of the algorithm provided by Provencher.¹³ TRAIIn solutions were obtained by the use of the algorithm provided by Xu and Zhang.⁷

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In our case, we have to consider first the distribution of $A(D)$ as a superposition of non-generalized Dirac's delta (Eq. 3 and SI).

$$A(D) = \sum_{i=1}^n \delta(d - D_i)|_{w} \quad (3)$$

Where n is settled as the number of non-generalized Dirac's delta that the DDGA will use to characterize the final number of components we are searching for, d is the feasible domain, D_i is the diffusion coefficient, and w is the uncertainty represented as the broadness of the Dirac's delta function solution. Thus, the fitness function could be reformulated as given by Eq. 4 (see SI)

$$\min F(A) \equiv f(D) = \left\| C \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n \delta(d - D_i)|_{w} - E_{diff} \right\|_2 \quad (4)$$

This new way to solve mixture problems can be established incorporating a natural evolution into an algorithm. Table S6 and Codes S2-S3 shows the implementation of the DDGA algorithm. The performance of our DDGA is illustrated by analyzing a blend of three monodisperse PS polymers in benzene- d_6 . The results afforded by some others regularization methods are also shown for comparison issues, and it will prove the strength of our approach regarding the accurate calculation on D -values, and eventually the correct prediction of the corresponding molecular weights.

We found that the PS mixtures were well-suited for the tests of multi-exponential fitting methods, because all the protons in the three PS systems are no-dependent on molecular weight and resonate at the same frequency. Figure 1 shows a rendering of the raw PGSE data for the blend of PS5950, PS60000 and PS1020000 in a 1:1:1 w/w ratio. Thus, the only way of distinguishing between them using NMR is to perform PGSE experiments and solve their diffusion coefficients.

Figure 1. Raw 1H NMR PGSE (STE) data showing the aromatic region of the blend of polymers in benzene- d_6 .

Analysis of the overall intensity attenuation showed how established algorithms such as ITAMeD (Figure S15), CONTIN (Figure S16) and TRAIIn (Figure S17) failed on calculating the diffusion coefficients of the PS mixture (Table 1), and only the

DDGA (Figure 2 and S14) successfully recovered accurate values, reproducing the data obtained from measurements of single component samples (Figures S11-S13),⁵ as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Diffusion values ($10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) at room temperature and diff errors (%)^a calculated through the different methods.

PS	ITAMeD	CONTIN	TRAI _n	DDGA
PS5950	0.1801	0.1760	0.1768	0.1975
diff (%) ^a	6.5	8.6	8.2	4.5
PS60000	0.0441	0.0414	^b	0.0507
diff (%) ^a	12.7	18.0	-	0.9
PS1020000	0.0011	0.0101	^b	0.0096
diff (%) ^a	88.3	7.4	-	2.1

^a With respect to D -values of 0.1926, 0.0505 and 0.0094 $10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for PS5950, PS60000 and PS1020000, respectively. ^b The smoothed nature of the solution inhibits D -value calculation.

Both ITAMeD and CONTIN could recover the diffusion coefficients of the three PS polymers of the blend, although not very accurately. For ITAMeD, the deviations are below 10% for PS5950, whether for PS60000 and PS1020000 the errors are of 12% and 88%, respectively. Interestingly, TRAI_n solution can only ascertain the D -value for the polymer of highest molecular weight, although with an error of 8.2%. In the case of DDGA, in the three circumstances the errors are below 5% with an average error of 2.5% for the whole range. Figure 2 illustrates the comparison between methods where the reference diffusion coefficients (dotted lines) were deduced by either monoexponential fitting of the signals obtained for single-compound samples, or by applying ITAMeD as published elsewhere.⁵ The grey spots in Figure 2 correspond to the centroids of the DDGA bars, which overlaid the reference dotted lines.

Figure 2. Comparison between ITAMeD (orange line), CONTIN (red line), TRAI_n (green line) and DDGA (black line and grey spots). Reference D -values are marked with dotted lines.

Centroid calculation and programming codes are provided in detail in the SI. The employed GA is the one already implemented in the Matlab® package, however, a comprehensive computational study was accomplished to find a suitable set of parameters. Thus, for populations sizes of *ca.* 10,000, the GA provided values of 0.025 when the fitness function was evaluated. When the population size was increased, the value of the fitness function decreased exponentially down to 0.005 (Figure S39). Moreover, if we observe how changes the fitness function along the uncertainty over discretization, population size and elite count, the convergence is reached when the function $[U/(D$

Ps Ec)] is of *ca.* 0.4 (Figure 40). All the optimized parameters together with the matlab code are given in the SI.

Consecutive executions of a GA in the same search domain for a fitness function must converge at the same solution or close to it. To prove its robustness, we run our DDGA four consecutive times employing a population size of 1000000 and an elite value of 20. The results revealed to be very robust and are shown in Figure S24 and Table S5. As mentioned before, the number of Dirac's delta functions used in the GA is the main factor in terms of computational cost, where the smaller the number the lower the amount of arithmetic operations per iteration the algorithm needs. When this number is rather small, it may not be enough to cover all the existing components present in the mixture and large errors in the calculation of the D -values are expected. On the other hand, when a large number of Dirac's delta functions is entered, it ensures to cover all molecules in the sample, at the expenses of longer computational cost. A trade-off between these two factors was found in our case by selecting three as the number of components, and spending 17 hours for the calculation of the D -coefficients (Table 2).

Table 2. DDGA Diffusion values ($10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)^a and UCC-predicted weight-average Mw for blend constituents.

PS	D	$D\eta$ (10^{-3})	A_v -Mw (Da) ^c	diff (%) ^d
5950	0.1975	0.1275	5372	9.7
60000	0.0507	0.0322	58811	0.4
1020000	0.0096	0.0058	1100199	7.8

^a ¹H PFG-STE measurements were performed at room temperature. ^b The viscosity value employed was η 0.646 $10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. ^c Estimated via the ITAMeD universal calibration curve $y = -0.5682x - 1.775$ ($R^1 = 0.9993$). See ref 5. ^d Considering the commercial values of 5950, 60000 and 1020000 Da.

The processing time for CONTIN was of the same order of magnitude as with DDGA, but for ITAMeD and TRAI_n the time elapsed were only seconds. All the calculations were run on a Windows 64-bits computer PC with an intel i7 3.5 GHz processor. The three DDGA D -values together with the recently described universal calibration curve (UCC) for PS samples,⁵ were employed for the weight-average Mw predictions. To our delight, the estimated Mw compared to real values (Table 2), fitted excellently well with errors below 6.0%. On the contrary, when the predictions are intended with the alternative algorithms, non-accurate weights are obtained, supporting the DDGA method as the most robust and reliable. To test the vulnerability to noise of our DDGA, we run Monte-Carlo simulations, where we could follow the dependence of the D -value with respect to the amount of experimental noise. Figures S20-S23 show the simulated distribution of attenuations at levels of noise from 0.1 to 10%, and the mean D -values and standard deviations provided in Table S3. The results were again comparable to compelling methods such as ITAMeD.¹⁹

In order to examine the scope of our method, the sample was also conducted for dynamic light scattering (DLS) experiments on a Malvern zetasizer instrument, a technique widely used in polymer chemistry. The software enabled collection of particle size distribution data as well as the absolute measurement of intensity. Figure S41 is the intensity size distribution obtained from the sample constituted by the three polymers in benzene- d_6 . The analysis showed two z -average radii (the mean radius based upon the intensity of scattered light) of 27.9 and 5.1 nm.

The first size fits reasonable well with the hydrodynamic radii of 34.7 nm obtained (through Stokes-Einstein)¹ when using the D -value of $0.0090 \text{ } 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for PS1020000. The second radius corresponds to the mean value of 4.5 nm, estimated from the two radii deduced for PS5950 (r_H 1.8 nm) and PS60000 (r_H 7.1 nm). This bimodal distribution confirms that DLS is not able to find the three systems under study, and reinforce the applicability of diffusion NMR for solving blends, with no matter the size of the components.

It is important to mention that when discovering discrete components, the DDGA shows outstanding results, comparable to ITAMeD, and remarkably, with computational times of the order of seconds. In fact, the application of both ITAMeD⁶ and DDGA, on a sample constituted of equal amounts of small molecules, provided almost equal results with differences below 6 % (Table 3).

Table 3. ITAMeD and DDGA Diffusion values ($10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)^a at room temperature for a mixture of small molecules.

Molecule	D , ITAMeD	D , DDGA	diff (%)
Acetone	2.44	2.59	5.7
Toluene	2.26	2.37	4.4
Chloroform	2.41	2.53	4.7
DCM	2.93	3.07	4.5
DMSO	1.90	1.99	4.5
ACN	2.71	2.87	5.5

^a ¹H PFG-STE measurements were performed at room temperature.

Figure 3 shows the different DDGA solutions for a sample containing all these small size molecules. The method can be routinely applied to mixtures where discrete resonances are observed as well as to mixtures in where the components have exactly the same chemical shift but different weight-average molecular weights, as it has been shown above.

Figure 3. DDGA solutions for a sample containing 10 μL of each molecule in CDCl_3 , where there are no overlapped resonances.

CONCLUSION

Mixture analysis is a complex task especially when the polymers have the same nature (comprise identical NMR spectra), and there are only differences in their molecular weight. We have described a DDGA which has been applied to PGSE diffusion NMR for the first time. The results showed that our approach reconstructs satisfactorily diffusion coefficients in a blend of polymers. A comparison with established methods such as ITAMeD, CONTIN and TRAIIn has been performed,

and showed that only DDGA did not fail in the estimation of accurate D -values and, thus, in the prediction of average-weight molecular weights. Similarly, DDGA has proven its strength and rapidness in small molecules discrete components, showing comparable performance and noise vulnerability to ITAMeD. The new algorithm outlined in this work is expected to be extremely useful for many applications in the polymer field, and specifically in the area of blends. Current work is focus on the programming of the algorithm towards faster performances.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Experimental section, complete NMR diffusion data (41 figures and 9 tables) and full programmed codes. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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SYNOPSIS TOC. A genetic algorithm that uses Dirac's delta functions has been applied for the first time in diffusion NMR, which reconstructs accurate diffusion coefficients in a blend of polymers.

